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DEVELOPMENT OF THE THEORY OF CALCULATION AND SELECTION OF PARAMETERS OF SYSTEMS FOR SEISMOISOLATION OF BUILDINGS AND STRUCTURES

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Annotation. This article discusses modern methods of earthquake quenching and seismic protection. A simple approach to solving the issue of seismic protection-the construction of a foundation with a sliding belt is recommended in increasing the earthquake resistance and strength of buildings. The use of this method allows you to reduce the cost of construction, while maintaining high reliability.

Key words: seismic isolation; seismically isolated buildings and structures; seismic resistance damping layer, active seismic isolation.

Introduction. Seismic isolation is one of the main ways to ensure the seismic resistance of buildings and structures. There are about 4,500 seismically isolated objects in the world. Among them, the most widespread are seismic insulation systems (SSI) on elastic belts with dampers of viscous or dry friction, as well as buildings and structures with a seismic insulating sliding belt. However, the theory of calculating the CSI has not been sufficiently developed to date. There is no consensus on setting up seismic damping. Many of the technical solutions used are considered controversial in terms of their effectiveness and safety. There are no uniform recommendations for the selection of seismic insulation parameters. The solution to the issues raised in the design is the correct modeling of the calculated seismic impact. For the last 20 years the basic requirements for the assignment of seismic effects for the deterministic calculation of seismically isolated systems are formulated. At the same time, seismic impacts should be considered as random processes. The problems of statistical modeling of vibrations of seismically isolated buildings and structures have been practically not covered in the literature. In this paper, the problem of statistical modeling of oscillations of the SI is considered, which makes it possible to choose an effective seismic isolation setting in statistical statements. The installation of seismic insulation systems is recognized worldwide as one of

the main means of ensuring the seismic resistance of structures. Many works of domestic and foreign specialists are devoted to the calculation, design and application of seismic isolation systems. Among them are the studies of Y.M.Eisenberg, I.U.Albert, T.A.Belash, T.J.Zhunuso va, D.Kelly, L.S.Kilimnik, A.V.Kurzanov, M.Melkumyan, S.V.Polyakov, V.Robinson, Y.L. Rutman, O.A.Savinov, R.Skinner, V.I.Smirnov, L.L.Soldatova, A.M.Uzdin, Z.G.Khuchbarova, Y.D.Cherepinsky, V.G.Yaremenko and other specialists. Thanks to their research, the general principles of the CSI device were developed and their high efficiency was shown when used correctly.

Materials and methods. The main result of the research carried out in the period from 1975 to 1985 was the substantiation of calculation schemes for the analysis of seismically insulated structures. Experts have analyzed various calculation schemes for modeling the operation of the CSI from the simplest to the most complex, involving finite element modeling of structures and foundations. The performed studies have shown that there is no need for detailed modeling of the seismically isolated part of the structure and the base when calculating the CSI. The calculation schemes used in the work of specialists are shown in Fig. 1. At the same time, a number of works note the insufficient seismic resistance of seismically insulated structures, and give examples of their collapse during destructive earthquakes. As the literature review has shown, the basic concept of earthquake-resistant construction of earthquake-insulated buildings and structures is as follows:

1. The seismic resistance of a seismically insulated structure is determined, as a rule, not by seismic loads and structural forces, which do not limit the operation of the structure, but by mutual displacements of seismically insulated parts and the strength of insulating supports, which necessitates the kinematic calculation of seismic insulation systems.

2. The assessment of the kinematic characteristics of seismic insulation requires a correct assignment of the calculated impact.

3. In order to limit the mutual displacements of the seismically insulated parts of the structure between the foundation plates in parallel with the seismically insulating support elements, it is necessary to install special damping devices. Dampers are the most important elements of the design scheme, and the justification of the required damping value is a special aspect of the theory of seismic isolation.

Fig. 1. Calculation schemes of varying degrees of complexity used to calculate a seismically isolated object

These principles are formulated on the basis of deterministic approaches that do not take into account the random nature of the seismic impact. The methods of statistical modeling of seismic impacts have not been sufficiently studied, and there are no methods for modeling them that take into account the effects that are important for calculating seismically isolated systems.

The above review shows that a large number of active seismic protection systems for buildings have been proposed and developed in our country and abroad. Some of these systems have been put into practice at individual facilities, which made it possible to assess their manufacturability for construction production. Vibration tests were carried out at many facilities, which made it possible to obtain experimental data on the behavior of these systems under dynamic influences. However, essentially all the developed systems need additional research, mainly in field conditions, since many aspects of the real behavior of seismic protection systems are difficult to study theoretically or on models due to the very large number of factors affecting the behavior of a structure during an intense earthquake.

Based on the existing experience of theoretical and experimental research, a number of promising seismic protection systems can be identified for earthquake-resistant construction:

- for 7- and 8-point districts for buildings with a rigid structural scheme, seismic insulation systems with rubber-metal supports, with kinematic foundations, systems with a flexible first floor with dry friction dampers can be recommended. In buildings with a metal frame, it is rational to use elastoplastic

absorbers, and for tall buildings with a metal frame, dynamic vibration dampers. For multi-storey frame-panel buildings, friction diaphragms can be recommended;

- in areas with a 9-point calculated seismicity, buildings with a rigid structural scheme with a seismic-isolating sliding belt in the foundation should be used mainly. For buildings with a frame structural scheme, switch-off and switch-on devices should be used communications.

The joint use of various seismic protection systems, the so-called combined systems, is promising, which allows combine their advantages and reduce the impact of adverse properties inherent in each of the systems separately. So, for example, for a building with one of the seismic isolation systems, supplemented with switching connections and a dynamic vibration dampener, it is possible to reduce the design load by one and a half to two points with any possible spectral composition of the earthquake.

Conclusions. In conclusion, we note that in cases where earthquakes with significant vertical accelerations are possible, the design of active seismic protection systems must be carried out taking into account both horizontal and vertical vibrations. Earthquakes are strong ground vibrations that occur due to the release of large amounts of energy over a short period of time during dislocations inside the Earth's crust or in the upper layers of the mantle. This is the point of view of seismology. For the national economy, an earthquake is a natural disaster that causes significant material damage and causes human casualties. The territories subject to seismic hazard with an intensity of 7-9 points account for about 15-20% of the total area of the CIS and are located mainly in the southern and eastern regions. Or another way is possible when using seismic isolation and other systems for dynamic regulation of seismic loads. The choice of a particular system, as well as calculation and design should be carried out with the participation of specialized design and scientific organizations. At the design stage, it is necessary to perform spatial calculations of buildings (ordinary buildings with a height of more than two floors, responsible and unique) for at least two computing complexes using variations of calculation models to eliminate the possibility of errors due to the accumulation of mathematical errors during the calculation. Currently, the following computing systems are used: SCAD, STARK, MicroFe, LIRA, Nastran, etc.

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